

The activity of selective sigma-1 receptor ligands in seizure models *in vivo*

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Running title: Seizure-modulating activity of selective sigma-1 receptor ligands

Abstract

Sigma-1 receptor (Sig1R) is a ligand-regulated protein which, since its discovery, has been widely studied as a novel target to treat neurological disorders, including seizures. However, the roles and mechanisms of Sig1R in the regulation of seizures are not fully understood. The aim of the present study was to test and compare effects of often used selective Sig1R ligands in models of experimentally induced seizures. The anti-seizure activities and interactions of selective Sig1R agonist PRE-084, selective Sig1R antagonist NE-100 and novel positive allosteric Sig1R modulator E1R were evaluated in pentylenetetrazol (PTZ) and (+)-bicuculline (BIC)-induced seizure models in mice.

Sig1R antagonist NE-100 at a dose of 25 mg/kg demonstrated pro-convulsive activity on PTZ-induced seizures. Agonist PRE-084 did not change the thresholds of chemoconvulsant-induced seizures. Positive allosteric modulator E1R at a dose of 50 mg/kg showed anti-convulsive effects on PTZ- and BIC-induced clonic and tonic seizures. The anti-seizure activity of E1R was blocked by NE-100. Surprisingly, NE-100 at a dose of 50 mg/kg induced convulsions, but E1R significantly alleviated the convulsive behaviour induced by NE-100. In conclusion, the selective Sig1R antagonist NE-100 induced seizures that could be partially attenuated by positive allosteric Sig1R modulator. Our results confirm that Sig1R could be a novel molecular target for new anti-convulsive drugs.

Keywords

Sigma-1 receptor, pentylenetetrazol, bicuculline, NE-100, E1R, anti-convulsive activity.

1. Introduction

Sigma-1 receptor (Sig1R) is a unique protein that regulates cellular protein functions, G-protein-coupled receptors and cell signalling molecules [1]. Sig1R has become increasingly studied as a target for medication development for neurological disorders, including seizures. This molecular chaperone protein can be regulated by several ligands. The classification of Sig1R ligands as agonists, antagonists and allosteric modulators is based on *in vivo* studies, which are necessary to fully describe and understand the pharmacological activity of Sig1R ligands.

The anti-convulsive activities of a number of selective Sig1R ligands have been studied mainly in glutamate- and opiate receptor-related chemoconvulsant induced seizure models *in vivo*. For example, high affinity Sig1R agonists, dextromethorphan (24 mg/kg, s.c.) and dimemorfan (24 mg/kg, s.c.), have prevented kainic acid-induced seizures in rats [2]. Similar activity has been shown for another Sig1R agonist, pentoxyverine, in rats on kainic acid-induced neurotoxicity [3]. Racemic (\pm)pentazocine co-administered with naloxone dose-dependently (20-100 mg/kg, s.c.) reduced tonic seizures induced by N-methyl-DL-aspartic acid in mice [4]. Antagonists of Sig1R, such as analogues of rimcazole (up to 60 mg/kg, i.p.), derivatives of BD-1008 (1-40 mg/kg, i.p.) and AC-927 (1-10 mg/kg, i.p.) protected against cocaine-induced seizures in mice [5-7].

Allosteric modulators of Sig1R have also demonstrated anti-convulsive activity. First described positive allosteric Sig1R modulator phenytoin [8] has been used in clinics against various types of epileptiform seizures for more than 70 years [9]. However, the antiepileptic activity of phenytoin is primarily related to the inhibition of voltage-gated sodium channels [10]. Recently the anti-convulsive effects of selective positive allosteric modulators of Sig1R SKF83959 (20-40 mg/kg, i.p.) and SOMCL-668 (40 mg/kg, i.p.) in models of pentylenetetrazol (PTZ)- and kainic acid-induced seizures were demonstrated to be mediated by modulating Sig1R [11]. Taken together, these data demonstrate that Sig1R ligands possess activity in models of experimentally induced seizures, but the roles and mechanisms of Sig1R in the regulation of seizures are not fully understood.

Selective Sig1R agonist PRE-084 and antagonist NE-100 have been widely used as pharmacological tools to study molecular mechanisms of Sig1R. PRE-084 is known for memory improving effects in pharmacological models of MK-801 and scopolamine-induced learning impairments [12], in the senescence-accelerated mouse model with age related cognitive deficits [13] and in animal models of Alzheimer's disease characterized by beta amyloid peptide-induced neurotoxicity [14]. PRE-084 has demonstrated also antidepressive activity [15] and neuroprotective properties in an ischemia-reperfusion-induced injury [16].

The *in vivo* activity of PRE-084 has been studied at a dose range from 0.1 to 60 mg/kg. In turn, NE-100 is used as a compound to confirm the selectivity of agonists on Sig1R sites. NE-100 has demonstrated anti-allodynic activity in capsaicin-induced mechanical hypersensitivity model [17]. In addition, a recently discovered Sig1R positive allosteric modulator E1R enhanced cognition and demonstrated efficacy against scopolamine-induced cholinergic dysfunction in mice [18]. It has been shown that E1R enhances the activity of PRE-084, while NE-100 blocks the *in vivo* effects of E1R [18]. Thus far the comparative anti-convulsive effects and interactions of Sig1R ligands have not been studied in the same experimental settings. Therefore, the aim of the present study was to test the seizure-modulating activity of selective Sig1R agonist PRE-084, selective Sig1R antagonist NE-100 and positive allosteric Sig1R modulator E1R in GABA-ergic signalling related chemoconvulsant PTZ and (+)-bicuculline (BIC)-induced seizure models in mice.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Animals

One hundred and forty-six, seventy-four, and thirty Swiss-Webster male mice were used in a PTZ-induced seizure model, a BIC-induced seizure model and an NE-100-induced seizure test, respectively. The mice weighed 25-40 g (Laboratory Animal Centre, University of Tartu, Tartu, Estonia). All animals were housed under standard conditions (21-23 °C, 12 h light-dark cycle) with unlimited access to standard food (Lactamin AB, Mjölby, Sweden) and water. All studies involving animals were conducted in accordance with ARRIVE guidelines [19,20]. Experimental procedures were performed in accordance with the guidelines reported in EU Directive 2010/63/EU and in accordance with local laws and policies. All procedures were approved by the Latvian Animal Protection Ethical Committee of Food and Veterinary Service in Riga, Latvia.

2.2. Chemoconvulsant-induced seizures

Chemoconvulsant-induced clonic and tonic seizures were initiated by inserting a 27-gauge needle into the tail veins and infusing 1% PTZ [21,22] or 0.01% BIC [23] at a constant rate of 20 μ l/2 s to restrained animals. The infusion was halted when forelimb clonus followed by tonic seizures of the full body were observed. Minimal doses of PTZ or BIC (mg/kg of mouse weight) necessary to induce clonic and tonic seizures were considered as indices of seizure threshold.

The activity of Sig1R ligands on clonic and tonic seizure thresholds was studied in PTZ- and BIC-induced seizure models and each experimental set included a respective control group. The minimal dose of PTZ and BIC to induce clonic and tonic seizures in each experimental group is expressed as percentage from control, where 100 % represents the seizure threshold for control group. Animals received i.p. injection of saline for control or Sig1R ligand 60 min before PTZ or BIC i.v. infusion. Each animal received a single dose of Sig1R ligand. In the PTZ-induced seizure model animals were divided in the following groups and experimental sets: saline (n=8) and PRE-084 at a dose of 3 mg/kg (n=8) for set number 1; saline (n=8), NE-100 at doses of 5 mg/kg (n=8) and 10 mg/kg (n=8) for set number 2; saline (n=10), PRE-084 at doses of 10 mg/kg (n=10) and 50 mg/kg (n=9), and NE-100 at doses of 25 mg/kg (n=8) and 50 mg/kg (n=7) for set number 3; saline (n=10) and E1R at doses of 10 mg/kg (n=9) and 50 mg/kg (n=10) for set number 4; saline (n=10), NE-100 at a dose of 5 mg/kg (n=10), E1R at a dose of 10 mg/kg (n=10) and group of combination of NE-100 at a dose of 5 mg/kg with E1R at a dose of 10 mg/kg (n=10) for set number 5. In the set number 5 NE-100 was administered 80 min before PTZ infusion (i.e., 20 min before E1R). In the set number 3 NE-

100 at a dose of 50 mg/kg induced seizures before PTZ infusion, therefore the animals (n=7) did not receive PTZ i.v. infusion and animal behaviour was observed and analysed separately (Material and methods section 2.3.). In total 146 animals were used in PTZ-induced seizure model.

In the BIC-induced seizure model animals were divided in the following groups and experimental sets: saline (n=10), PRE-084 at a dose of 50 mg/kg (n=10) and E1R at a dose of 50 mg/kg (n=10) for set number 1; saline (n=10) and E1R at a dose of 10 mg/kg (n=10) for set number 2; saline (n=8) and NE-100 at doses of 10 mg/kg (n=7) and 25 mg/kg (n=9) for set number 3. In total 74 animals were used in this model.

2.3. NE-100-induced seizures

NE-100 at a dose of 50 mg/kg (n=7) induced seizures before PTZ i.v. infusion, therefore animal behaviour was observed separately. The number of animals with seizures, the latency time until the first occurrence of seizures and duration time was analysed. Further, the NE-100-induced seizures were studied at a dose of 75 mg/kg, which induced seizures in 11 from total of 11 animals (n=11). To compare the activities and interactions of the Sig1R ligands, the animals received selective Sig1R agonist PRE-084 (n=6) and positive allosteric Sig1R modulator E1R (n=6) at the same dosages as that of NE-100. In total 30 animals were used to observe, analyse and describe the seizures induced by NE-100. Compounds or saline were administered 30 min prior to NE-100. Mice were then placed immediately in observation chambers (40×25×15 cm) and video recorded for 25 min using a digital HD video camera recorder (Handycam HDR-CX11E, Sony Corporation, Tokyo, Japan). Scoring scale for observed behavioural responses of animals was adapted from previously published seizure rating scale [24]. Behavioural responses of animals were scored from the video files using the following scale: 0, no abnormality; 1, trembling or wobbly gait; 2, tail lifting; 3, clonic seizures while lying on belly; 4, tonic seizures while lying on belly; 5 clonic-tonic seizures while lying on belly; 6, motionless or sleeping; 7, clonic seizures while lying on side; 8, tonic seizures while lying on side; 9, clonic-tonic seizures while lying on side; 10, generalised seizures with wild jumping and running. If the animal died during the observation period the score of 11 was given for the rest of time points. Maximal score was given for each 20-second period. Latency time until the first occurrence of seizures induced by NE-100 was also determined from the video files.

2.4. Data and statistical analyses

The results are expressed as the means \pm S.E.M. The data for the chemoconvulsant-induced seizures were analysed using Student's t-test and one-way ANOVA followed by Newman-Keuls multiple comparison test. The statistical calculations were performed using GraphPad Prism 3.0 (GraphPad Software, Inc., La Jolla, California, USA). P-values less than 0.05 were considered significant.

2.5. Chemicals

(4R,5S)-2-(5-Methyl-2-oxo-4-phenyl-pyrrolidin-1-yl)-acetamide (E1R) was obtained from JSC Grindeks (Riga, Latvia). 2-(4-Morpholinethyl) 1-phenylcyclo-hexanecarboxylate hydrochloride (PRE-084) and 4-methoxy-3-(2-phenylethoxy)-*N,N*-dipropylbenzeneethanamine hydrochloride (NE-100) were purchased from Tocris Bioscience (Bristol, UK). PTZ and BIC were procured from Sigma-Aldrich Co. (St. Louis, MO, USA). 0.9% physiological saline was purchased from Fresenius Kabi (Warszawa, Poland). PTZ was weighed and dissolved in 0.9% physiological saline to make a 1% PTZ solution. BIC was dissolved in DMSO to prepare a 1% stock solution, which was then diluted with saline to make a 0.01% BIC solution. PTZ and BIC solutions were freshly prepared before each experiment. Compounds were dissolved in saline before use.

3. Results

3.1. Activity of selective Sig1R ligands in the PTZ-induced seizure model

The 1% PTZ i.v. infusion induced clonic and tonic seizures in control animals at a dose of 24 ± 1 mg/kg and 67 ± 8 mg/kg, respectively. To test activities of Sig1R ligands, compounds were administered 60 min before PTZ. Selective Sig1R agonist PRE-084 tested at doses of 3, 10 and 50 mg/kg did not change animal behaviour and the threshold for PTZ-induced seizures (Figure 1). Surprisingly, we discovered that the i.p. administration of selective Sig1R antagonist NE-100 at a dose of 50 mg/kg induced convulsions in mice before PTZ infusion. Therefore, animals from these group were excluded from the experiment, and the behaviours of these mice were further observed (the results are described in section 3.4.). At a dose of 5 mg/kg NE-100 had no effect on seizure thresholds (Figures 1 and 3). The administration of NE-100 at a dose of 10 mg/kg showed a tendency for pro-convulsive activity on PTZ-induced clonic seizures. NE-100 at a dose of 25 mg/kg demonstrated significant pro-convulsive activity on PTZ-induced clonic seizures (Figure 1). NE-100 had no effect on tonic seizures (Figure 1). Positive allosteric Sig1R modulator E1R demonstrated dose-dependent anti-convulsive effects on PTZ-induced tonic seizures (Figure 1). E1R given i.p. at a dose of 10 mg/kg significantly increased the thresholds for clonic seizures by 20% and for tonic seizures by 47% (Figure 1). The thresholds on PTZ-induced clonic and tonic seizures increased by 23% and 75%, respectively, after the administration of E1R at a dose of 50 mg/kg (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Comparison of Sig1R ligands on PTZ-induced seizure thresholds. Dotted line represents threshold for PTZ-induced seizures in control group (100%). Arrow up shows that compound increases seizure thresholds (>100%) and possess anti-convulsive activity. Arrow down shows that compound decreases thresholds (<100%) and possess pro-convulsive activity. Compounds were administered i.p. 60 min before PTZ injection. Data are expressed

as the means \pm S.E.M. (n=8-10 in each group). * p <0.05 vs. control, # p =0.05 vs. control (Student's t-test).

3.2. Activity of selective Sig1R ligands in the BIC-induced seizure model

The selective Sig1R ligands were also tested on BIC-induced seizures. Clonic seizures in control animals were induced at a dose of 0.49 ± 0.06 mg/kg of BIC. BIC-induced tonic seizures were induced at a dose of 0.96 ± 0.15 mg/kg. PRE-084 administered at a dose of 50 mg/kg demonstrated no differences compared with the control group on the BIC-induced seizure thresholds (Figure 2). The administration of NE-100 at a dose of 10 mg/kg had no effect on the seizure thresholds. NE-100 at a dose of 25 mg/kg showed a slight tendency for pro-convulsive activity in the model of BIC-induced clonic seizures. E1R given at a dose of 50 mg/kg significantly elevated the thresholds on BIC-induced clonic and tonic seizures by 21 and 25%, respectively (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Comparison of Sig1R ligands on BIC-induced seizure thresholds. Dotted line represents threshold for PTZ-induced seizures in control group (100%). Arrow up shows that compound increases seizure thresholds (>100%) and possess anti-convulsive activity. Arrow down shows that compound decreases thresholds (<100%) and possess pro-convulsive activity. Compounds were administered i.p. 60 min before BIC injection. Data are expressed as the means \pm S.E.M. (n=7-10 in each group). * p <0.05 vs. control (Student's t-test).

3.3. Anti-seizure effects of E1R are Sig1R dependent

To verify that Sig1R was involved in the anti-convulsive activity of E1R, we used selective Sig1R antagonist NE-100. For PTZ-induced seizures, pre-treatment with NE-100 alone at a dose of 5 mg/kg had no significant effect on seizure thresholds (Figure 3). E1R given at a dose of 10 mg/kg significantly increased the threshold on PTZ-induced tonic seizures by 39%

(Figure 3). The administration of NE-100 (5 mg/kg) before E1R (10 mg/kg) significantly restored the tonic seizure threshold to the basal level (Figure 3) and therefore, showed that the anti-seizure effect of E1R was mediated through Sig1R activity.

Figure 3. Effect of selective Sig1R antagonist on the anticonvulsive activity of E1R on PTZ-induced seizures. Dotted line represents threshold for PTZ-induced seizures in control group (100%). Arrow up shows that compound increases seizure thresholds (>100%) and possesses anti-convulsive activity. Arrow down shows that compound decreases thresholds (<100%) and possesses pro-convulsive activity. E1R was administered i.p. at a dose of 10 mg/kg 60 min before PTZ injection. NE-100 was given i.p. at a dose of 5 mg/kg 80 min before PTZ injection. Data are expressed as the means \pm S.E.M. (n=10 in each group). * $p < 0.05$ vs. control, # $p < 0.05$ vs. E1R (One-way ANOVA followed by Newman-Keuls multiple comparison test).

3.4. NE-100 per se induces seizures in mice after systemic administration

I.p. administration of NE-100 at doses of 50 and 75 mg/kg induced convulsions in mice. Convulsive activity after the administration of NE-100 at a dose of 50 mg/kg was observed for 5 from total of 7 animals. The convulsive behaviour in mice started approximately 9 min after NE-100 (50 mg/kg, i.p.) administration and lasted until 20 min (data not shown). NE-100 at a dose of 75 mg/kg induced generalised, tonic and clonic seizures for 11 from total of 11 animals. Convulsions started approximately 4 min after NE-100 (75 mg/kg, i.p.) injection (Figure 5A). During the 25-min observation time, seizures appeared periodically, and 10 different behavioural categories were observed in the mice (Figure 4). First observed behavioural response after administration of NE-100 at a dose of 75 mg/kg was trembling

together with wobbly gait (animals were looking dizzy). NE-100-induced seizures started with tonic seizures followed by clonic-tonic seizures. After that seizure intensity increased and clonic, tonic and clonic-tonic seizures were observed while animal lied on side. This quite rapidly resulted in generalised seizures (approximately 6 min after NE-100 injection). The average time of the first occurrence (onset latency) for each behavioural category is shown in Figure 4. During the later periods (after 25-min observation time), the animals remained motionless and slowly regained their normal behaviour. After administration of NE-100 at a dose of 75 mg/kg four animals died during the first 15 observation min (Figure 6B).

Figure 4. Onset latencies of the different behavioural categories after NE-100 administration: trembling or wobbly gait (TR/W), tail lifting (Tail), clonic, tonic and clonic-tonic seizures while lying on belly (C, T and C-T up, respectively), clonic, tonic and clonic-tonic seizures while lying on side (C, T and C-T side, respectively), generalised seizures with wild jumping and running (G), motionless (ML). Data are expressed as the means \pm S.E.M. ($n=11$).

3.5. The activity of selective Sig1R ligands on NE-100-induced seizures

PRE-084 and E1R at a dose of 75 mg/kg partially prevented NE-100 induced seizures and showed lower average behavioural score (Figure 5A, Table 1). However, as demonstrated by the data expressed as areas under the curve (AUCs), only E1R effect was statistically significant (Figure 5B). In addition, 2 and 1 animals in the PRE-084 and E1R, respectively, did not have any seizures after the administration of NE-100. E1R significantly reduced also the number of animals with generalised seizures induced by NE-100 and reduced the generalised seizure count per animal, whereas PRE-084 had no effect (Figure 6A). E1R also demonstrated higher latency times until the first occurrence of seizures induced by NE-100

(Table 1). However, there was no significant difference when compared with the NE-100 treated animal group (Table 1).

Figure 5. The activity of PRE-084 and E1R on NE-100-induced convulsive behaviour. PRE-084 (75 mg/kg, n=6), E1R (75 mg/kg, n=6) or saline (n=11) were administered i.p. 30 min prior to i.p. injection of NE-100 (75 mg/kg). **(A)** Average behavioural scores for each group during 25-min observation period. Data are expressed as the means for each 20 s period. **(B)** The area under curve (AUC_{0-1500s}) was calculated from behavioural scoring curve. Data are expressed as the means ±S.E.M. (n=6-11). * $p < 0.05$ vs. the saline group (One-way ANOVA followed by Newman-Keuls multiple comparison test).

Figure 6. The effect of Sig1R ligands on NE-100-induced generalised seizures and survival. PRE-084 (75 mg/kg, n=6), E1R (75 mg/kg, n=6) or saline (n=11) were administered i.p. 30 min prior to i.p. injection of NE-100 (75 mg/kg). **(A)** Effects on NE-100-induced generalised seizures. Data are expressed as the means \pm S.E.M. * $p < 0.05$ vs. the saline group (One-way ANOVA followed by Newman-Keuls multiple comparison test). **(B)** Survival curve during 25-min observation period.

Table 1. The activity of Sig1R compounds on NE-100-induced convulsive behaviour.

	Saline + NE-100	PRE-084 + NE-100	E1R + NE-100
Animals with seizures, n/total n	11/11	4/6	5/6
Seizure onset time, s	238 \pm 27	239 \pm 35	320 \pm 34

Animals with generalised seizures, n/total n	11/11	4/4	1/5
Average maximal score (peak)	8.2 ±0.8	5.7 ±1.9	5.8 ±1.3
Average time to reach peak, s	569 ±65	330 ±59	708 ±166
Average behavioural score	5.3 ±0.3	3.6 ±0.2	3.3 ±0.2

PRE-084 (75 mg/kg; n=6), E1R (75 mg/kg; n=6) or saline (n=11) were administered i.p. 30 min prior to i.p. injection of NE-100 (75 mg/kg).

4. Discussion

The seizure-modulating activity of selective Sig1R agonist PRE-084, antagonist NE-100 and E1R, a positive allosteric Sig1R modulator, has never been described previously. In this study, we report for the first time the pro-convulsive and convulsive activity of selective Sig1R antagonist NE-100, whereas we did not observe any activity on PTZ- and BIC-induced seizures for Sig1R agonist PRE-084. In turn, Sig1R positive allosteric modulator E1R showed anti-convulsive effects both on PTZ- and BIC-induced clonic and tonic seizures. Interestingly, the effect of E1R was blocked by Sig1R antagonist NE-100, and the NE-100-induced convulsive behaviour was partially attenuated by E1R.

NE-100 is a selective Sig1R antagonist ($K_i=0.86$ nM) displaying more than 55-fold selectivity over Sig2R and more than 6000-fold selectivity over dopamine, serotonin and phencyclidine receptors [25]. We found that NE-100 induced convulsions already after a single injection in mice. Previously only Sig1R agonist-induced dose-dependent convulsive behaviour has been described for (\pm)-pentazocine [26] and (+)-3-PPP [27]. (\pm)-Pentazocine-induced seizures started with forelimb and head jerks followed by minor vibrissae twitching and facial jerks, and continuous forelimb and head jerks for first 20 min, but during the later period, animals remained motionless and slowly regained normal behaviour [26]. (+)-3-PPP elicited behavioural clonic or tonic-clonic convulsions within 3-6 min from the administration of the drug [27]. These behavioural seizures lasted for 3-5 min and were followed by death of some animals [27]. In our study we found that Sig1R antagonist NE-100 during 25 min observation period induced clonic, tonic, clonic-tonic and generalised seizures and also resulted in death of some mice. Similarly as for (\pm)-pentazocine, after the 25-min observation time NE-100-treated animals became motionless and later regained their normal behaviour. Overall, it can be concluded that both Sig1R agonists (\pm)-pentazocine and (+)-3-PPP and Sig1R antagonist NE-100 demonstrate similar convulsive activity and animal behaviour in experimental studies, which raises questions about activities of Sig1R ligands in the light of classic models of receptor agonism and antagonism.

In addition to *in vivo* induced seizures after single administration of NE-100, we found that NE-100 presents a dose-dependent pro-convulsive activity in PTZ- and BIC-induced seizure models. Previously, the pro-convulsive activity has been shown for Sig1R agonist (+)-pentazocine, which dose dependently (12.5-50 mg/kg, s.c.) reduced seizure threshold in flurothyl-induced seizure model [28]. However, in the same study structurally related Sig1R agonist (+)-cyclazocine demonstrated dose-dependent (2.5-10 mg/kg, s.c.) anti-convulsive activity [28]. In another study racemic (\pm)-pentazocine has demonstrated dose-dependent (10-50 mg/kg, i.p.) anti-convulsive activity on maximal electroshock-induced seizures [29].

Additionally, (\pm)-pentazocine dose-dependently (20-100 mg/kg, s.c.) reduced tonic seizures induced by N-methyl-DL-aspartic acid [4]. The role of Sig1R in flurothyl-induced seizures remains controversial, since (+)-pentazocine and (+)-cyclazocine possess opposite effects, even though both are Sig1R agonists and have binding affinities in the nanomolar range ($K_i=3$ nM for (+)-pentazocine; $K_i=17$ nM for (+)-cyclazocine) [30]. The anti-convulsive activity has been shown for Sig1R agonists dimemorfan (24 mg/kg, s.c.) and carbetapentane (12.5 and 25 mg/kg, i.p.) in kainic acid-induced seizure model [2,3], dextorphan (20-40 mg/kg, i.p.) in maximal electroshock-induced seizure model [31], and dextromethorphan in models of kainic-acid- and maximal electroshock-induced seizures (24 mg/kg, s.c. and 20-40 mg/kg, i.p., respectively) [2,31]. In turn, it has been shown that Sig1R agonists SA-4503 and 1,3-di(2-tolyl)guanidine (DTG) cannot protect against cocaine-induced seizures, while in the same study Sig1R antagonist panamesine demonstrated anti-convulsive activity [7]. Similar activity has been shown for Sig1R antagonists AC-927 (1-10 mg/kg, i.p.), LR-172 (1-30 mg/kg, i.p.) and BD-1047 (1-40 mg/kg, i.p.) on cocaine-induced seizures [5,6]. However, there is limited information available about activity of Sig1R antagonists in other seizure models. For example, in kainic-acid-, maximal electroshock- and PTZ-induced seizure model Sig1R antagonist BD-1047 possess seizure modifying activity, but the compound was used only at low doses (1 and 2 mg/kg, i.p.) [2,3,11]. Our results for the first time show the pro-convulsive activity of a selective Sig1R antagonist in GABA-ergic system-related chemoconvulsant seizure models and provide evidence for the involvement of Sig1R in processes of PTZ- and BIC-induced seizures.

Many studies have suggested the potential therapeutic use of Sig1R antagonists for the management of neuropathic pain. Selective Sig1R antagonists, such as BD-1063, BD-1047, E-52862, S1RA and NE-100 have been shown to attenuate the development of hypersensitivity in models of neuropathic pain in mice and rats [17,32,33]. It should be noted that above listed Sig1R antagonists in the respective studies have been used at quite high doses. For example, NE-100 administered s.c. at doses of 32, 64 and 128 mg/kg significantly reduced capsaicin-induced mechanical hypersensitivity in mice [17]. Additionally, the effects of S1RA on mechanical hypersensitivity induced by capsaicin in mice were studied at a dose of 64 mg/kg after i.p. and at a dose of 128 mg/kg after per oral administration [34]. Thus, the effective doses of NE-100 used to treat neuropathies are very close or even higher than doses shown to induce convulsions in our study. Side effects, such as cognitive impairment, have already been shown at the highest doses (500-800 mg p.o.) of S1RA in phase I clinical studies [35]. These effects should be seriously considered when studying Sig1R antagonists as novel drug candidates.

Surprisingly, our study demonstrated that Sig1R agonist PRE-084 neither had anti-seizure nor pro-convulsive nor convulsive activity up to a dose of 75 mg/kg. PRE-084 has a high affinity to Sig1R ($K_i=2.2$ nM) [36]. DTG, a Sig1R and Sig2R agonist, has demonstrated anti-convulsive properties on BIC-induced seizures. However, the effects of DTG were not blocked by non-selective Sig1R antagonist haloperidol [37]. It seems that anti-seizure activity of Sig1R agonist compounds does not involve effects on GABA-ergic signalling.

Previously we showed that E1R, a phenylpiracetam derivative, is selective positive allosteric Sig1R modulator [18,38]. In this study E1R showed anti-convulsive effects both in PTZ- and BIC-induced seizure models. Some other known positive allosteric modulators of Sig1R, such as phenytoin and ropizine [8], SKF83959 [39], and SOMCL-668 [11] also have demonstrated anti-convulsive activity. Similarly as in the present study, the anti-convulsive activity of SKF83959 and SOMCL-668 in the PTZ-induced seizure model was blocked by a selective Sig1R antagonist BD-1047 [11]. This allows us to confirm the anti-convulsive properties of positive allosteric Sig1R modulators and the role of Sig1R in the mode of action of these compounds. Among all positive allosteric Sig1R modulators, E1R is the only one known modulator that possesses memory-improving effects [18]. Phenytoin treatment on epilepsy has been shown to induce learning and memory deficit. Add-on approaches for the management of memory deficits associated with conventional anti-epileptic drugs are needed [40]. The effects of E1R show that it might be a promising novel anti-seizure drug with no negative influences on memory typically encountered for many anti-epileptic drugs.

In conclusion, for the first time, our study demonstrates the pro-convulsive and convulsive activities of selective Sig1R antagonist NE-100. NE-100-induced convulsive behaviour can be partially attenuated by positive allosteric modulation of Sig1R. Additionally, the obtained results suggest that Sig1R could be considered as a molecular target for new anti-convulsive drugs.

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